

THE EFFECT OF ENVIRONMENT ON THE DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF GLASS AND CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: An examination of the damage tolerance of two distinctly different performance (carbon and glass fibre reinforced epoxy prepreg) composites, each targeted at separate ends of the engineering market were put into context by subjecting them to environmental extremes. The conditioning was chosen such that it reflected likely scenarios in industry and facilitated an accelerated programme of testing. The observed response of each material to its particular environmental conditioning is discussed and the immediate implications of these findings commented upon, within the realms of their potential application. Subsequently, the interpretation and relevancy of the damage tolerance test for these extreme conditions was put into perspective.

KEYWORDS: accelerated testing, environmental conditioning, compression after impact

INTRODUCTION

Compression after impact test data obtained under elevated temperature or moisture conditions requires careful interpretation compared with room temperature tests. This is due to reduced fundamental strengths at high temperature and moisture and/or changes in failure mechanism induced by impact or subsequent compression testing. This paper examines the behaviour of two well characterised materials, under extreme conditions of temperature and environmental exposure and compares the results to room temperature tests.

MATERIALS

Two principal reinforcement fibre types, carbon and glass, were used in this study and subjected to extreme (accelerated) environmental conditions commensurate with their industrial applications e.g. carbon - aerospace and glass - chemical and marine.

The material tested under a range of high temperature impact and compression after impact conditions, was an Hexcel (formally Ciba Composites) 924C (a toughened epoxy with the Torayca T800H carbon fibre).

For the hygrothermal investigation, Hexcel's (formally Ciba Composites) 913 resin system was reinforced by E-glass.

The carbon and glass fibre laminates' lay up consisted of a 16 ply quasi-isotropic construction as follows: $[-45,0,45,90]_{2s}$. Both unidirectional prepreg tape stacks were cured in accordance with their respective recommended resin cure cycles - 913 @ 120 °C and 924 @ 180 °C. All the material was non-destructively inspected prior to testing using ultra-sonic C-scan and any defective material rejected.

The fibre volume fraction in the carbon laminates was estimated to be 60% based on the cured thickness (nominally 2 mm).

The fibre content in the glass laminates was determined by resin burn off to be approximately 55%.

TEST METHODS

The thermal conditioning, Table 1, of the carbon fibre composite was representative of trans and supersonic temperatures generated in aircraft skins arising from kinetic heating.

The impact specimens were preheated in an oven to an over temperature and removed for testing. An instrumented specimen was manufactured to calibrate the temperature time behaviour to ensure impact occurred in the desired temperature range.

Table 1: Impact and compression after impact test matrix for 924C

Impact Temperature (°C)	Compression after Impact Temperature (°C)	
20	20	150
80	20	80
150	20	150

Laminates for the hygrothermal element of the investigation resulted in one set of three being immersed in a temperature controlled bath of water at 70°C for six months before being tested. A second set was impacted over an energy range prior to conditioning for six months, while the third set was used as a control and not subjected to any environmental extremes.

All the laminates were cut into specimens, 89 mm long and 55 mm wide, using a liquid cooled diamond saw.

The impact and compression after impact tests were performed using inhouse equipment. The specimens, supported on a 40 mm ring were struck by a 20 mm diameter hemisphere weighing 3.96 kg. Complete details regarding the post impact compression jig, and its derivative for elevated temperature testing, may be found elsewhere [1]. Elevated temperature undamaged plate compression testing was also conducted using the modified compression after impact jig for insitu heating. All mechanical testing was carried out on a screw driven Instron 1195 at a controlled constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min.

The impact induced delamination extents in the carbon and glass fibre laminates were determined using ultra-sonic C-scan. In the case of the carbon fibre laminates these

specimens were also re-scanned after the residual compression phase to qualitatively measure delamination propagation.

RESULTS

Elevated Temperature Testing

Impact

To facilitate ease of comparison, the 924C room temperature results are incorporated to define a baseline against which performance changes may be measured.

The impact induced delamination damage extent increases not only with incident energy, but also with increasing temperature, Figure 1. This is particularly evident for the data generated at 150 °C. At the highest impact energy level (6 J) used for this material, the room temperature delamination spread has been observed to approach the support dimensions, thus the measured damage extent for the high temperature impact may be in error as they may be constrained by the boundary conditions.

Figure 1: Damage extent versus impact energy over a range temperatures

Undamaged Plate Compression Strength

The ‘undamaged plate compression strength’ decreases monotonically with increasing temperature, Figure 2.

The plate compression tests conducted at 80 °C, unlike the room temperature tests failed at the base support and not the unsupported region, in a splaying or brooming mode. At 150 °C similar fracture characteristics occur, however, the failure region is less extensive, the high temperature having softened the matrix sufficiently to allow the composite to yield.

Figure 2: Undamaged plate compression strength as a function of temperature

Compression After Impact

Figure's 3a and 3b present the compression after strength versus impact energy and damage extent respectively for all the temperature combinations used, normalised with respect to the 'undamaged plate compression strength' at that temperature.

Figure 3a: Normalised residual compression strength versus impact energy over a temperature range (impact temperature/compression after impact temperature)

The trends indicate, Figure 3a, that there is a slight improvement in the normalised residual strength retention when the compression phase is performed at 150 °C, although there is little or no apparent difference between room temperature and 80 °C strengths. However, when the normalised residual strength is plotted against damage width, Figure 3b, the samples compression tested at 150 °C now clearly show a higher relative strength retention compared to those tested at room temperature and 80 °C.

Figure 3b: Normalised residual compression strength versus damage extent over a temperature range (impact temperature/compression after impact temperature)

Hygrothermal Testing

Moisture Diffusion

Gravimetric analysis indicated that the glass/epoxy laminates resembled Fickian diffusion, although continued moisture uptake may occur through other mechanisms [2]. Visual observation revealed that the specimens developed an opacity, with blisters occurring on the outer plies after approximately two months exposure.

Impact

To facilitate ease of comparison, unconditioned data are incorporated to define a datum against which changes may be determined. The impact induced delamination damage extents in the unconditioned and six month environmentally (70 °C water) exposed glass/epoxy are plotted as a function of impact energy, Figure 4. The data demonstrate that samples conditioned actually contained delamination damage better than the benchmark specimens.

Figure 4: Damage extent versus impact energy with and without conditioning

Compression After Impact

The compression after impact data are presented in the classical fashion, that is, against incident energy, Figure 5a.

Figure 5a: Compression after impact strength versus impact energy for all conditions

The absolute trends indicate that the detrimental effect of delamination damage is exacerbated by the addition of environmental exposure. The subtle difference being between those samples that were conditioned then impacted and those that were impacted then conditioned.

This affect is magnified when considering the residual strength on the basis of the delamination damage extent, Figure 5b, and infact the presence of any impact induced damage may be disregarded inview of the almost non-existent rate of strength loss with increasing impact energy or damage extent, provided, a measure of the undamaged strength of an exposed laminate is known.

Figure 5b: Compression after impact strength versus damage extent for all conditions

DISCUSSION

Carbon/Epoxy

While the 924C may not be the ideal candidate material choice for a second generation Concorde due to its instability at prolonged high temperature exposure, it may be indicative of the behaviour of the better suited resin systems, e.g. Bismaleimides (BMI) or polyimides.

The reduction in plate compression strength may only be representative of a trend, however, there is sufficient experimental evidence available clearly stating this link, much of it attributing this behaviour to fibre instability through a reduced matrix shear modulus [3-5].

Examination of the 924C's compression after impact results, Figures 3a and 3b, demonstrate some interesting characteristics - the elevated temperature residual (normalised) compression strengths are higher for a given impact energy than the room temperature results, and especially so if the impact themselves were generated at the high temperatures. This effect is accentuated if the data are analysed on the basis of damage extent. On this Figure (3b), a line has been drawn which divides all the data generated by compression testing at 150°C and room temperature, such that the elevated temperature data lie above this line and the room temperature below.

This behaviour may be partly explained by the post failure ultra-sonic C-scan of the specimens, Figure 6. The interpretation may be that as the temperature in the compression phase increases so the corresponding delamination propagation band decreases, suggesting that the effective delamination extent is reduced [1].

Figure 6: Schematic representations of room temperature impact and the subsequent propagation of delaminations at: i) room temperature and ii) 150 °C

Glass/Epoxy

The trends observed in the carbon/epoxy composite in terms of undamaged strength may also be achieved through an increased presence of moisture in the composite. This, acting concert with the hydrophilic nature of glass fibres (attack of the interface leading to irreversible degradation) may further reduce fundamental properties [6].

The reduction in damage extent in the conditioned samples may be due to plasticisation of the matrix and reduction of the interfacial bond. This concentration of damage was linked to an increase in crack density through the thickness of the laminate beneath the point of contact [7]. This mechanism may be more severe than wide spread delamination and might responsible, in conjunction with general matrix and fibre/matrix degradation, for the poor compression after impact strength. However, the presence of damage prior to exposure may be expected to further encourage fracture through extension of existing matrix and delamination cracks leading to further reductions in residual strength, but this was not the observed behaviour and may be due more to the changes in basic strength through exposure.

An Interpretation of the CAI Relevancy to Extreme Condition Testing

The combinations of test conditions for the carbon/epoxy specimens listed in the matrix (Table 1) reflect a range of potential temperatures when impact may occur, however, it must be emphasised that these specimens were mechanically unstressed, which, particularly at high temperatures, may not be the case as the aircraft may be in flight. Consequently, the damage may be greater, resulting in possible catastrophic failure by either penetration or immediate delamination propagation induced by the pre-stressed state of the structure. Similar concerns may be raised in regard the data generated by the hygrothermal testing.

Conventional wisdom has had the compression after impact strength analysed solely on the basis of impact energy. The behaviour of the materials investigated in this programme clearly showed that this may lead to erroneous interpretations of the data.

It is a recipe for disaster if the essential elements of composite durability are not incorporated in damage tolerance tests as room temperature data may not be extrapolated. The performance of the 924C is surprisingly good when compared on the basis of its undamaged strength at temperature, exceeding that of the room temperature data. This result may not have been expected given the increase in damage extent with temperature.

In contrast, the mechanisms associated with hygrothermal testing may at first glance appear insignificant, in terms of undamaged strength for these conditions, however, the near penetration of the laminate may have more serious consequences.

It has been argued in previous papers that the accepted approach to compression after impact test analysis, whereby the residual strength is assessed as a function of impact energy is misleading [8,9]. This is because the separate phenomena of damage creation and damage propagation are not distinguished. The environmental influence of either temperature or exposure to moisture clearly exacerbates this problem. In some instances damage size is largely irrelevant, in others strength is linked to initial damage size. In some cases all damage propagates (sideways), in others only partial propagation occurs. Consequently, simple trends observed between materials at room temperature and without long term environmental exposure can not be assumed to continue under more aggressive test conditions. Materials

that appear relatively good (compared to others) at room temperature and low humidity can not be relied upon to hold the same relative position in any table of performance with hot or wet test conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

The link between impact damage size and the residual compression strength varies according to the temperature at testing and the environmental history of the specimen.

Now that composites are readily achieving more extensive acceptance among engineering sectors it is now critical that stock is taken of where these materials have reached new applications and examine their suitability, before a catastrophic failure results in confidence being undermined and their usage set back a number of years.

Misadventure and a lack of understanding of what the damage tolerance test provides may require more infrastructure around the basic test to facilitate better judgement and interpretation of the materials suitability to the chosen application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC), the Defence Research Agency (DRA) and the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) for supporting this programme of work.

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